

<p align="center">SYNTACTIC AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF LITERALLY IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE</p>		<p align="center">Semantics and Syntax</p> <p>Keywords: idioms, lexical items, Albanian students, Albanian equivalent, syntactic structure, verbal and non-verbal idiom, comparative method, William Shakespeare, Geoffrey Chaucer, Ismail Kadare, Sami Frashëri, etc.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p> <p>Both English and Albanian languages are highly idiomatic. Idiomatic phrases are meaningful as a whole or complete items rather than a collection of separate words. Idioms are created from the free word-groups, which in the course of the historical development of English and Albanian languages have acquired semantic and grammatical inseparability. We may also say that idioms are derived from different fields and those that are derived from more specific domains are likely to differ across cultures. Classification of idioms in both languages Albanian and English is the same in phraseological context, i.e., lexical form. It differs in historical, cultural and geographical accidents but sometimes they share common culture. When defining Albanian and English idioms, they are similar in three levels: <i>semantic, lexical and syntactic</i>.</p>		

Introduction

We should present more idioms to the students with a focus on exposing students to the target language culture. Students face difficulties during the teaching process of idioms learning. Different strategies, approaches techniques methods can be used by my opinion analyzes approach can help a lot. A linguistic feature can be expressed in different forms of language. In our opinion, natural approach can be taken in consideration because it gives opportunity to guess appropriate meaning of idioms and to teach the idioms spontaneously. However, grammar approach cannot be avoided. In order to improve student’s communication skills different methods can be used:

- Dialogue method (especially for primary school students)
- Work in pairs
- Interactive method
- Group method and
- Demonstrative method

Inductive Reasoning

English and Albanian idioms are an important part in both languages. They come up all the time in both written and spoken. Because idioms don’t always make sense literally, it’s a need to familiarize with the meaning and usage of each idiom. We have tried to find some idioms used in novels written by some famous writers such as William Shakespeare, Geoffrey Chaucer, Ismail Kadare, Sami Frashëri, and other worldwide known. Most of these idioms have been translated in either language. Learning to use common idioms and expressions will make your English sound more native, so it’s a good idea to master some of these expressions.

Every language has its own collection of wise sayings. They offer advice about how to live and also transfer some underlying ideas, principles and values of a given culture, society. These sayings are called "idioms" - or proverbs if they are longer.

These combinations of words have (rarely complete sentences) a “figurative meaning” meaning, they basically work with “pictures”. That may seem like a lot of work, but learning idioms is fun, especially when you compare English idioms to the idioms in your own language. Idioms are theoretically challenging class of lexical items, because they share the characteristics of both words and phrases. Provided that among different languages there exists the reciprocal giving and receiving or linking bridges such as idioms, which contain common meanings, knowledge of these linking bridges enables the best and fastest learning of a certain language. Meanwhile, considering the fact that idioms express a part of a nation’s culture, the following paper aims at comparing certain groups of literal idioms, both in English and Albanian. In meantime examination of literal idioms which can undergo changes in meaning in one of the languages will not be averted. Except for the comparisons, the following paper aims at making the sources of the idioms, their meanings in the respective languages, the cultural contacts which have enabled the use of these idioms in both languages evident. Also, it will not be possible to avoid reviewing idioms that may have meaningful changes in one of the languages. Certain idioms retain the same meaning during parallel use in Albanian and English. Idioms can be taught by using different forms and methods. I have chosen exercises which can help students recognize, teach, understand and use the idioms properly.

Hypothesis Research

The following hypothesis will be validated in this research:

- a. The similarities and differences of the phrases used will be found in some English and Albanian literary novels;
- b. Recommendations will be given for the equivalent classification of these phraseological expression;
- c. Recommendations will also be given for their proper translation as well as for understanding their meaning, given the difficulties encountered in translating and understanding some of the idioms used;
- d. It will be ascertained at what frequency the idioms expressions are used in these selected novels;
- e. Learning English idioms is very important to Albanian students;
- f. Bringing the Albanian EFL students as closer as possible to English culture helps them learn English idioms easier. It is vitally important for teachers of English to bring students as closer as possible to English culture in order to teach idioms to them.

Methodological Framework

a) Comparative method, analyzing and comparing in equivalent and quantitative terms the idioms used in some English and Albanian novels.

b) Research method, by researching English novels of Shakespeare and Albanian novels especially Kadare's, in order to more easily understood and translate the idiomatic expressions used in these selected novels.

Comparative Method

The essential principle we utilized to examine the idioms is correspondence. I have tried to define correspondence semantically, i.e., the comparison of idioms centers on the meaning of the idiom as a whole and such meaning is composed of the meanings of its individual members. With most idioms in the corpus, the most important member of the idiom is a noun consequently the comparison concerns this member. The correspondence is then based on the fact whether this central component is identical in the languages chosen for comparison. Since my comparison is based on the semantic criterion those idioms which lack this key component can still be seen as corresponding providing the overall meaning of the idiom is identical. As an example, we have the English “*fight tooth and nail*” and the Albanian “*luftoj dhëmb për dhëmb*” (literally translated as fight tooth for tooth). These two idiomatic expressions have identical meaning; they are regarded as corresponding although the Albanian idiom lacks the word nail. Thus they are not considered totally correspondent but partially correspondent. Some of the English and Albanian body idioms have been analyzed into four categories according to their equivalence:

1. *Absolute correspondence* the compared idioms correspond on all three levels, i.e. on the semantic, lexical and formal level. E.g., 1: All ears/eyes – *gjithë tërë sy e veshë* this category covers idioms that have the same meaning and allow the same syntactic structure of a verbal or non-verbal idiom.

2. *Close correspondence* they are similar in meaning, use the same syntactic structure and correspond on the lexical level, nevertheless, they show small differences on the morphological level. E.g., 2: “Arm in arm – *krah për krah*”

3. *Partial correspondence* this subcategory includes all idioms, which correspond only on the semantic level. They are lexically non-equivalent or show differences in the syntactic structure. E.g., 3: “Face to face – *ballë për ballë*”. The whole idioms is expressed with different lexical means however, there is no change in the semantics of the idioms.

4. *Non-correspondence* is regarded as a wide category. It contains idioms, which do not have any correspondent, but it also comprises idioms, which are expressed non-idiomatically.

E.g., 4: “At first hand” – “*nga burime të drejtpërdrejta*”. (Gaba: 2018: pp.185–187)

Examples of Idioms from Novels Translated From English into Albanian and From Albanian into English

William Shakespeare's Idioms Semantically and Syntactically Analysed

William Shakespeare's known as one of the most successful authors of English literature such as drama, poetry and verse. But we must emphasize that he is known for the ability to write through each he invented many words and idioms. These inventions helped to improve, modernize, expand, and standardize the English language. He belonged to the authors who were the inventors of idioms and the invention of hundreds of new words which are still in use today.

He used idioms in various dialogues in his literature to show the speech patterns and nature of a character. He is known as the first person to use but also popularize many expressions and idioms in his dramas. Finally we can mention that the idioms he invented are still in use today.

Example 1: "*Cruel to be kind*" Hamlet 1994:108. – "*Sjam zemër gur, përveç nga dashuria*" Shqipëroi Fan. S. Noli 2001: 145

Hamlet was meeting with her mother while Polonius was snooping to make sure whether Hamlet was really mad or just pretended to be mad. When he noticed someone's snooping, Hamlet mistook Polonius with Claudius. So he ran towards him and ended his life. When Hamlet realized the person he killed was Polonius, he said *cruel to be kind*. It's obvious that Hamlet felt guilty when he realized he murdered the wrong person. So people may think of the words as Hamlet's self-comfort and an excuse of his guilt. But I think there's another purpose worth to be considered: Hamlet said these in order to stir his mother. As we all know, Hamlet's mother remarry with Claudius after his father died of poison. Hamlet was ashamed of it. His willingness of revenge is strong. He may already knew that the meeting was tentative in order to make sure whether he was mad or not. So he may convey a message like this: my justice must be done no matter whether it's violent, bleeding or "*cruel*". He must be cruel to his mother now (kill her partner to revenge) to save her from falling into the hell of betrayal and sensuality at present. This may be just the right "*kind*" to her.

The compared idioms are similar in meaning use different lexemes and follow different syntactic structure such as in English: Adj + Prep + Verb + Adj, were in Albanian: Verb + Noun + Adj + Prep + Prep + Noun.

Example 2: "*There's the Rub*" - Hamlet 1994:81 "*oh, këtu ngeç*" Shqipëroi Fan. S. Noli 2001: 145.

The phrase is Shakespeare's. It comes from Hamlet's famous "To be or not to be" soliloquy: To die – to sleep. To sleep. To sleep-perchance to dream: ay, **there's the rub!** For in that sleep of death what dreams may come. When we have shuffled off this mortal coil. Must give

us pause. By *rub*, Hamlet means a difficulty, obstacle or objection — in this case to his committing suicide.

The idioms are similar in meaning, lexically non-equivalent and follow different syntactic structure in English: Pron Verb + Art + Noun, were in Albanian: Inter +Adv + Verb.

Example 3: “*To be or not to be*” Hamlet 1994: 81 – “*Të rrosh, a të mos rrosh*” Shqipëroi Fan. S. Noli: 105.

“*To be or not to be*” is one of the most famous lines in all of English literature. It marks the beginning of Hamlet’s “*To be or not to be*” speech which is a soliloquy. The speech and the line reflect some of the existential questions that *Hamlet* play and Hamlet the character are interested in. A soliloquy is a speech made by one character. The speech does not actually represent spoken words but the thoughts and feelings of the character speaking (therefore, it is assumed that even if other characters were to “listen in” on a character who is giving a soliloquy as Polonius and Claudius do, they would not really hear the speaker, in this case Hamlet.)

The idioms are same in meaning use similar lexemes and follow same syntactic structure in English: Prep + Verb + Conj + Adv + Prep + Verb, were in Albanian: Prep + Verb + Conj + Prep + Adv + Verb.

Example 4: “*Wild goose Chase*” Romeo and Juliet 1994:71 – “*Ndjek lojën e patës*” Përktheu: Kristo 1997: 73

Romeo: Switch and spurs, switch and spurs; or I’ll cry a match.

Mercutio: Nay, if thy wits run the wild-geese chase, I have done, for thou hast more of the wild goose in one of thy wits than, I am sure, I have in my whole five. Our current use of the phrase alludes to an undertaking, which will probably prove to be fruitless – and it’s hard to imagine anything more doomed to failure than an attempt to catch a wild goose by chasing after it. Our understanding of the term differs from that in use in Shakespeare’s day. The earlier meaning related not to hunting but to horse racing. A “wild goose chase” was a race in which horses followed a lead horse at a set distance, mimicking wild geese flying in formation.

The idioms are semantically similar, close correspondence in lexemes and follow different syntactic structure in English: Adj + Noun + Verb, were in Albanian: Verb + Noun + Conj.

Example 5: “*Wear my heart on my sleeve*” Othello 2005:7 – “*E marr ate zemër dhe e hedh ta hanë galat*” Shqipëroi Fan. S. Noli 2012: 1.

This phrase may derive from the custom at middle ages jousting matches. Knights are said to have worn the colors of the lady they were supporting, in cloths or ribbons tied to their arms. The term doesn't date from that period though and is first recorded in Shakespeare’s Othello, 1604. In the play, the treacherous Iago’s plan was to feign openness and vulnerability in

order to appear faithful. Iago: It is sure as you are Roderigo, Were I the Moor, I would not be Iago: In following him, I follow but myself; Heaven is my judge, not I for love and duty, But seeming so, for my peculiar end: For when my outward action doth demonstrate. The native act and figure of my heart. In compliment extern, 'tis not long after. *But I will wear my heart upon my sleeve.* For dawns to peck at: I am not what I am.

The idioms are semantically similar use different lexemes and follow different syntactic structure in English: Verb + Pron + Noun + Prep + Pron + Noun, were in Albanian: Conj + Verb + Prep + Noun + Conj + Verb + Conj + Verb + Noun

Example 6: “*Love is Blind*” The Merchant of Venice 1946: 79 – “*Dashuria është e verbër*”.

This expression is first found in Chaucer's *Merchant's Tale*. For **loue is blynd**alday and maynat see. It didn't at that stage become a commonly used phrase and isn't seen again in print until Shakespeare took it up. It became quite a favorite line of his and appears in several of his plays, including *Two Gentlemen of Verona*, *Henry V* and this example from *The Merchant of Venice*, 1596:

JESSICA: Here, catch this casket; it is worth the pains. I am glad 'tis night, you do not look on me, for I am much ashamed of my exchange: But *love is blind* and lovers cannot see. The pretty follies that themselves commit; for if they could, Cupid himself would blush. To see me thus transformed to a boy.

Absolute correspondence on the semantic, on the lexical level follow the same syntactic structure in English: Noun + Verb + Adj, were in Albanian: Noun + Verb + Conj + Adj.

Example 7: “**Break the ice**” Timing of the shrew 1842: 136 – “*Thyej akullin*” Përktheu Stefanllari, 1998: 3.

This phrase was first used in *The Taming of the Shrew*. Tranio encourages Petruchio to “*break the ice*” with Katherine to get to know her, suggesting that he may like her better - and get her to like him. Today this phrase is used to refer to relieving tension or getting to know someone better, usually by making small talk, or a kind gesture to start a new relationship.

They have exactly the same lexical form, and both mean ‘to overcome initial difficulty in starting a conversation. Idioms correspond on all three levels, i.e. on the semantic, on the lexical and follow similar syntactic structure in English: Verb + Art + Noun, were in Albanian: Verb + Noun.

Transmission of Idiomatic Expressions with the Same Meaning Value from Albanian to English Written by Ismail Kadare

In this issue, I will present some cases where the transmission of the idiomatic expressions meaning values in the translation language is the same as in the source language. In cases where the meaning of the cultural language may be equal from one language to another, it greatly helps the translator in the translation process, without creating problems and difficulties in finding them. The main aim of this article is to investigate how different cultural aspects of source text are transmitted into the target text, causing cultural losses. As we might know, cultural losses are defined as the losses of cultural norms, social customs, idioms, and proverbial wisdom that are inherited through generations and comprise the identity of the source culture.

In this sense, we argue that figurative language and cultural terms of the source text are unfamiliar for target text and they should be looked at from the perspective of a cultural insider. Example 1: Çdo njeri, që ka dy parë mend, e kupton menjëherë se pa ne, pa seleksionimin, interpretimi mbetet si “*mulliri pa ujë*”. (P.Ë., f.53) – English: anyone with the least gumption can see that without us here in selection, interpretation would be like “*a mill without any wheat*”. (P.D., p.24)

The Process of Learning English Idioms at School

The aim of this chapter is to investigate the difficulties students face during the process of translating idioms, mainly the problem of non-equivalence. It also aims at identifying learner’s strategies in interpreting both familiar and unfamiliar idioms, from English into native language and vice versa, especially when they do not find a direct equivalence in the target language. This chapter provides also details about the research strategy adopted to check the hypothesis together with the means used to collect data for analyzing it, including site and sample selection, and the analysis approach adopted in this research. Language is an instrument for social interaction. The structure of language reflects not only its grammatical features, but uses its functional and communicative in speech. A linguistic feature can be expressed in different forms of language; therefore, students are presented with different forms of language to a certain function.

Taking into consideration the great importance of idioms, and believing in the difficulties that may be posed while translating this type of figurative language, the main aim of this study is to examine the type of difficulty students of English face in translating idioms, and try to suggest solutions and identify strategies that may help to limit or avoid these difficulties. The present study is a linguistic investigation of equivalence above word level. It deals with the difficulties of non-equivalence posed in translating English idioms into another language and vice versa, and the methods used by students to find the suitable equivalent in the target language. The aim of this study is to examine the type of difficulty students at a high school “Josi Broz Tito” in Manastir (Bitola), face while translating idioms and tries to suggest solutions and identify strategies that

may help to limit or avoid these difficulties. In this respect, some exercises are made up of some English idioms students to be translated. The results of the study show that there are potential problems in the process of translating idioms from English into native language and vice versa.

Furthermore, the findings show that the context of use helps many students of English to guess the appropriate meaning of idioms. They also confirm our hypothesis and reveal that, except word for word translation, students’ use of other translation strategies is limited. As regards idioms, it will be used the following techniques:

- Follow the rules given in the text
- Finding the idioms in the texts
- Comparison of mother tongue with a foreign language
- Memorizing grammatical structures and frequent use of them.

As students, use these techniques. Translating idioms is one of the most difficult tasks for translators. The main problems consist in recognizing an idiom, understanding it and distinguishing idiomatic from non-idiomatic usage. The results of the study show that there are potential problems in the process of translating idioms from English into native language and vice versa. Furthermore, the findings show that the context of use helps many students of English to guess the appropriate meaning of idioms. They also confirm my hypothesis and reveal that, except word for word translation, students’ use of other translation strategies is limited. Moreover, similar notions like metaphors and clichés, proverbs and fixed expressions are also discussed and compared to idioms in order to highlight the main differences between them, and provide a clear image for students about idioms. This study involved 40 students with good English from 1-4 years in high school “Josip Broz Tito” in Manastir (Bitola). The instrument used in this study is exercises. Students completed the survey by using appropriate exercises.

Exercises 1: Look at the idioms. Can you guess their meaning?

- | | | |
|-------------------------------|------------------------|---------------------|
| hold your breath | kiss something goodbye | hit the roof |
| think twice (about something) | kick the habit | drop someone a line |

Complete the sentences. Use the idioms above.

1. The best way to stop hiccups is to _____ your _____ and count to ten.
2. My parent’s _____ the _____ when I said I’d been to an all-night party.
3. I’ve tried so many times to stop biting my nails, but I just can’t _____ the _____.
4. I almost bought a new sports car, but then I _____ _____ about it and realized it wasn’t such a great idea.
5. **A** I lost my purse with £200 in it.
B Well, you can _____ that money _____!
6. _____ me a I _____ when you what time you’re coming, and I’ll meet you at the station.

Exercise 2: vocabulary and idioms. Work in pairs which parts of the body do you use to: kick; chew; lick; stare; bite; think; stare; point; hold; climb; kiss; hit; whistle; hug.

Exercise 3: Read the text and identify the idioms, underline them and match them with the verb or expression. For example: **Look out!** That dog is going to bite you!

Exercise 4: In these pairs of sentences, one meaning of the phrasal verb is literal and the other word is idiomatic. Say which is which.

1. a The plane has just *taken off*.
- b Please *take off* your coat and sit down.

Exercise 5: In which one these sentences are the word in *italics* used literally. Rephrase the words used metaphorically. Can you give me *a hand* to move this sofa? It's so heavy.

Exercise 6: Add some new idioms in both Albanian and English if you know any.

Teaching Idioms by Using Pictures

Provide a picture to explain the context. This works best if you show an image that humorously illustrates the literal meaning of the idiom. It will make students laugh, but also help them understand or guess what a phrase means. Idioms are full of colorful imagery, perfect for a flashcard or photo. Show the picture to your students and have them guess the meaning of the idiom. From there, give examples of when you would use it and how the words and the actual meaning of the idiom are different. Looking for a good resource? Check out this website for an example of great images to explain the meaning of idioms. And for some beautiful images depicting idioms, be sure to check out this site.

Use small groups to present dialogues

Break your class into small groups and have each group look up two idioms. Dave's ESL Cafe has a great collection of idioms and their meanings for student reference. Before they look them up, have the students make an educated guess on what the idiom means, and then let them search for the real meaning. Have students explain the meaning to the rest of the class and use the idiom in a short sample dialogue.

"Introduce Amelia Bedelia"

No, Amelia! You don't actually *throw* the tent into the woods! You don't have to be a kid to adore Amelia Bedelia and her literal mind. She's the perfect teacher for an idiom lesson. Visit the publisher's website for activities, book excerpts, Worksheets and games. While the material is oriented for children, it's also a great way for older students to learn English idioms through a fun and quirky character!

Conclusion

In short, translating idioms is one of the most problematic issues for ESL/EFL student learners. The meaning is considered as the main leading cause to failure in achieving the appropriate translation of a particular idiom, because it may confuse those not already familiar with these idioms. One feature that characterizes all idioms is that it should be learned and used as a single unit of language in order to end up with a meaningful expression meaning. Students, however stick to word for word strategy because they think that the use of other strategies may change the words of the idiom and hence, changes its meaning. But this strategy is not always appropriate in such a type of translation. In case of transparent and semi-transparent idioms, it may help students to infer the meaning of the idiomatic expression through the meaning of its parts. But, for opaque and semi-opaque idioms, it is impossible to do so, because taking into consideration the meaning of the idiom individual parts may totally confuse students.

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